

Full Length Article

Metal-induced crystallization of amorphous semiconductor films: Nucleation phenomena in Ag-Ge films

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ABSTRACT

The initial stages of interfacial interactions between Ag nanoparticles and amorphous Ge (a-Ge) films, in particular the mechanism and kinetics of metal-induced crystallization (MIC) of a-Ge films are investigated herein. Unsupported Ag-Ge films formed by PVD were used as a model. *In situ* high-resolution (S)TEM and low-loss monochromated STEM-EELS techniques were used for real-time observation of the nucleation and growth of crystalline Ge and intermediate phases, as well as mapping of chemical elements at the reaction zone. We show that crystallization is activated at the metal–semiconductor interface around ≈ 200 °C, followed by lateral crystallization of a-Ge film at temperatures above ≈ 400 °C. It was revealed that the MIC process occurs through intermediate phases. Metastable $\text{Ag}_{0.8}\text{Ge}_{0.2}$ hcp phase was identified at the reaction front at elevated temperatures, thus revealing the non-equilibrium melting of a eutectic alloy as the most probable mechanism of Ag-induced crystallization of a-Ge film. We show that the MIC process is activated only if the size of Ag nanoparticles exceeds a critical value, which is ≈ 8 nm in our case and equal to the thickness of the a-Ge film.

1. Introduction

Thin crystalline Ge and Si films are key materials for novel electronics, optoelectronics, and photovoltaic technology. However, Si or Ge films grown from the vapor phase are usually amorphous and thus, their crystallization requires external stimuli to undergo a transition from the metastable to the equilibrium state. Thermal annealing, stresses, as well as electron and laser beam irradiation are examples of external stimuli [1–7] that trigger the aforementioned transition. Thus, annealing of amorphous Ge (a-Ge) films induces its crystallization within the temperature range 400–590 °C. It has been found that the crystallization temperature depends on film thickness. In fact, as the thickness of the a-Ge film is reduced, a higher temperature is required to crystallize it [6–8]. Intense electron or laser irradiation might also trigger local crystallization of a-Ge films even at room temperature. This effect occurs almost instantaneously and is termed *explosive crystallization*. It is believed that this process is intermediated by melting, i.e. a local increase of the temperature under the irradiation pulse yields the formation of a thin liquid layer. The liquid is substantially undercooled, and its

rapid crystallization results in the growth of semiconductor crystals. The latent heat released at the crystallization front drives the reaction further resulting in radial dendritic growth around the irradiated region, extending to tens of μm in distance [1–4]. This process becomes self-sustaining, crystallizing the entire volume of the film, at substrate temperatures greater than some critical value, which mostly depends on the material, thickness, and thermal conductivity.

Another way to crystallize amorphous semiconductor films is to bring them in contact with a metal (e.g. Au, Ag, Al, Bi, Sn, Pd, Zn), such that a eutectic couple is formed [8–12,14–20]. In this case, the crystallization temperature of the amorphous film is reduced significantly, which could be as low as 87 °C for Au/Ge, and 75 °C for Sn/Ge couples [19]. Furthermore, it scales with the eutectic temperature of the binary couple, i.e. crystallization starts around 2/3 of the eutectic temperature [8–10]. The effect is commonly referred to as “metal-induced” or “metal-mediated” crystallization (MIC). The formation of complex morphologies, metastable solid solutions, as well as mass transfer on large scales are typical outcomes of the MIC process in layered films (see [11–14,21] and references therein). Despite more than 50 years of research [18,19],

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a fundamental mechanism of the MIC reaction is still under debate in the literature. Many authors believe that MIC is a pure solid-state reaction involving the dissolution of Ge and Si into a metal, followed by their precipitation in the crystalline phase [8,16,20], while others defend that the formation of an intermediate liquid phase occurs at the reaction zone [9,10,15]. The major argument against the liquid-phase mechanism is the absence of reliable observations of intermediate phases (even metastable) during the MIC reaction [16,20]. Nevertheless, both solid-state and liquid-phase mechanisms are phase transformations of first order and, hence, should involve nucleation and growth stages of a crystalline phase.

In this regard, the primary objective of the work is to understand and identify the MIC mechanism, by investigating the initial stages of the MIC process. *In situ* aberration-corrected TEM/STEM coupled with EDS and EELS were utilized to study the nucleation phenomena at MIC, down to the atomic level.

2. Materials and methods

We used silver-germanium (Ag/Ge) films as a model system. Ag/Ge films with Ag nanoparticles on a-Ge film were formed by thermal evaporation of pure components from Al₂O₃ cylindrical crucibles, in a vacuum of 1×10^{-7} mbar. The Ge and Ag were sequentially deposited on freshly cleaved KCl single-crystals at room temperature. The thickness of the Ag and Ge films was monitored by a quartz crystal microbalance. The evaporation of Ag from a crucible has specific features, namely, uneven heating of the crucible generates turbulence in the Ag melt and causes a sudden release of Ag nanodroplets. In this regard, we benefited from the non-stationary evaporation process of Ag and used spitting from the effusion cell to produce Ag nanodroplets in the specimens along with an ordinary island film. Furthermore, we varied the fraction of the spitted nanodroplets in the evaporation flux by tuning the evaporation conditions, thus producing specimens with different morphologies of the Ag film. The Ag/Ge films were separated from the substrate by dissolving salt crystals in distilled water and transferred onto through-hole MEMS-based chips for *in situ* TEM investigations. In this fashion, we obtained freestanding Ag/Ge samples in the area of interest of the chip (fig. S1 in the supplement materials).

In situ TEM studies were performed using a double corrected FEI Titan G3 Themis 60–300 operated at 200 kV, fitted with a NanoEx-i/v MEMS-based single-tilt heating holder (installed at the International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory). The temperature of the sample was incremented in 50 °C steps between 25 °C and 500 °C. A beam current of 1 nA was used to minimize the radiation damage of the films.

In situ STEM-EELS investigations were conducted in the 350–450 °C temperature range using a probe corrected FEI Titan G2 60–300 TEM equipped with Wildfire D6 double-tilt heating holder (DENSSolutions) and Gatan Image Filter (model 966) at 80 kV (hosted by AGH UST). Post-heating STEM coupled with EDX, as well as diffraction studies were carried out at 200 kV. Low-loss EELS spectrum images (SI) 100 × 100 pixels in size were acquired with a pixel size of 1.7 nm and a dwell time of 10 ms. Convergence and collection semi-angles of 12.5 mrad were used. The electron beam current of ≈8 pA was used in EELS SI experiments, resulting in a radiation dose $1.7 \cdot 10^5 \text{ e}^-/\text{nm}^2$ per SI image, which is comparable to that of a single 1024×1024 pixels STEM image acquired at the same magnification with a current of 80 pA and a dwell time of 10 μs. Excitation of the electron gun monochromator ensured an energy resolution of 0.23 eV (FWHM) for the zero-loss peak. Chemical element distribution maps were constructed using Ag and Ge low loss peaks in the EELS spectrum. Subsequently, to reduce the noise of the Ag plasmon and Ge M-edge spectral data, we used the principal component analysis (PCA) plug-in [22] for Digital Micrograph™ software, while Ge plasmon maps were constructed using the raw SI data. Finally, smoothing was used to produce less pixelated images. The intensity scale of EELS maps was almost similar for each quantity in the temperature series.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. As deposited films

Fig. 1 shows TEM images of two Ag/Ge specimens, studied in the work. Both specimens are perfect model samples for studying the interfacial interactions between Ag NPs and a-Ge film.

The first specimen (Fig. 1 a-c) consisted of crystalline Ag NPs with sizes ranging from 25 to 80 nm and randomly distributed on the amorphous and continuous Ge film. The Ag particles were mostly single-crystalline as shown by the Fourier Transform (FFT) (Fig. 1c) of the image corresponding to particle P1 (Fig. 1b). The local thickness of the a-Ge film was ≈10 nm as assessed by EELS from the ratio of zero-loss electrons to the total transmitted intensity of the spectrum.

The second specimen had Ag NPs of 4–7 nm in size, which were uniformly covering the a-Ge film, along with rare Ag NPs with sizes ranging from 50 to 120 nm. Fig. 1d shows a region with two large (62 and 90 nm size) Ag NPs in the field of view. These large NPs were the result of the non-stationary evaporation process. On the other hand, the fine NPs were formed via the Volmer-Webber growth of Ag on a-Ge (Fig. 1e). These fine NPs have fcc crystalline structure, as shown by the phase contrast TEM image in Fig. 1f, with the lattice constant of Ag. It is also worth noting a granular structure of the as-deposited a-Ge film, which is clearly visible in the HAADF-STEM image (Fig. 1e). The size of the a-Ge granules was found to be 8–10 nm, which is comparable with the Ge film thickness. Please also note that each fine Ag NP is located in the center of a granule of the a-Ge film (inset in Fig. 1e).

3.2. Nucleation phenomena

The nucleation and growth of the crystalline Ge phase was observed at the atomic scale in real-time by heating specimen 1 in TEM. Two distinct regimes of the a-Ge crystallization process were clearly observed for this configuration of the Ag/Ge film. In the first regime, which occurs at low temperatures, the process occurred at the Ag–Ge interface only, i. e. under the Ag nanoparticle. This was confirmed by a slight variation in the image contrast of the Ag NPs observed already at 200 °C, indicating the onset of the interaction process at the particle-Ge interface. The area of interaction grows with the increase in temperature (Fig. 2S in the supplement materials), but unfortunately, we were not able to identify the phases formed during this regime, due to the large size of the Ag NPs, which resulted in poor image contrast. The second regime of the reaction, which is the lateral crystallization of a-Ge film, was initiated at temperatures above 400 °C. In this case, nuclei formed at the Ag-Ge interface advanced towards the free areas of the a-Ge film. One of these nuclei caught at the edge of Ag NP P2 (Fig. 2a) exhibited a spherical shape with a size of ≈8 nm (Fig. 2b). Its crystalline structure was identified as an Ag_{0.8}Ge_{0.2} hexagonal alloy (ICSD Code 58274) oriented close to the [211] zone axis (Fig. 2c). During the experiment, the nucleus was not stable. In fact, it was motionless for a few seconds, and then advanced to an adjacent region of a-Ge in a jump-like manner, leaving crystalline Ge behind. The process repeated itself countless times, crystallizing a-Ge around the parent Ag NP, i. e. it was self-sustained at this temperature. This is clearly visible from the video sequence (see Video1.avi in the supplement materials). Fig. 3 shows a series of frames from this video along with the FFT spectra from the marked region, revealing the kinetics of MIC process. First, a-Ge in the rectangular region in Fig. 3a is transformed to hcp AgGe structure (Fig. 3b) due to the advancement of the nucleus, which was generated by the Ag NP. c-Ge phase in this region appeared just behind the advancing hcp AgGe nucleus (Fig. 3c). Hence, the MIC process could be described by a-Ge + Ag → hcp AgGe → c-Ge + Ag transformation, i. e., it occurs through the intermediate phase. At the same time, a disordered phase is visible along with the hcp structure in the FFT spectrum (inset in Fig. 3b). There is no support film, therefore, it belongs to Ag/Ge film. The nature of the disordered phase is unclear yet. This could be the

Fig. 1. Aberration-corrected TEM/STEM images of two specimens of Ag/Ge film: sample 1 – (a-c), and sample 2 – (d-f). a) Bright-field TEM image of the MEMS chip hole containing the Ag/Ge film specimen #1; b) Phase contrast TEM image of particle P1 in (a); c) Fast Fourier transform of image (b) confirming the fcc Ag structure of the particle P1; d) HAADF STEM image of the ROI of the specimen 2; e) HAADF STEM image of fine Ag nanoparticles located on a-Ge labeled by the yellow square in (d); f) Phase contrast TEM image of an individual Ag NP revealing its crystallinity. The inset in (e) shows a HAADF-STEM image of a granule of the a-Ge film with an Ag NP in the center. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Phase contrast TEM images (a, b) of AgGe hcp nucleus at 450 °C and FFT of (b) indexed to AgGe hcp phase (c). Dot line in (a) outlines the area of MIC reaction at the Ag-Ge interface.

remains of a-Ge film, but we speculate that a non-equilibrium liquid phase might be forming at the reaction front. HR TEM contrast from amorphous and liquid phases is similar, which makes them indistinguishable in the images. Furthermore, the nearest-neighbors' distances in a-Ge and liquid AgGe eutectic alloy are almost similar [23] and unresolved by radial distribution function analysis of FFT spectra of Fig. 3. Therefore, additional studies of the formation and temporal stability of metastable liquid and hcp phases are required for further insight.

Every large Ag NPs generated AgGe nuclei, ultimately resulting in the crystallization of the whole volume of the a-Ge film. It is worth noting that an increase of the temperature to 500 °C did not change the

pattern of the MIC process. The crystallization of a-Ge occurred in the same manner, yet with the nuclei moving with a slightly higher speed. The movement of the nuclei was terminated once they were fully surrounded by the crystallized regions of Ge film. At the same time, the regions of Ge film without the presence of Ag NPs remained amorphous at 500 °C, confirming the decisive role of Ag in activating the crystallization process.

3.3. Kinetics of MIC probed by low-dose EELS

In situ TEM studies revealed the presence of an intermediate hcp

Fig. 3. Time series TEM images of the same area of Ag/Ge film at 450 °C showing the propagation of a nucleus and crystallization of a-Ge film. FFT spectrum in the inset corresponds to the rectangular region. Arrows in TEM images indicate the direction of the nucleus advancement. Dot arcs in the inset in (c) correspond to crystalline Ge.

structure in the reaction zone. This phase has a lattice parameter similar to the AgGe hcp alloy, yet phase contrast TEM images are unable to prove the presence of Ag in the reaction zone. To address the issue, we have used low-loss STEM-EELS spectral imaging, which is ideal for mapping Ag and Ge at the MIC reaction front, without substantial radiation damage of the area under study. In this technique, the focused electron beam is scanned over a selected region and the EELS spectrum is acquired in each point of the raster. Plasmon resonance peaks of Ag and Ge, and Ge-M ionization edge were used for elemental mapping at different stages of the MIC reaction.

In this regard, specimen 2 (Fig. 1 d-f) was used in this part of the study. The crystallization of a-Ge was activated at the Ag/Ge interface followed by the lateral crystallization of a-Ge film (see fig. S3 in the supplement materials). We traced the MIC reaction around particles P3 and P4 (Fig. 1d) using EELS spectral imaging, however, instead of continuously recording the reaction, as it was done in the previous section, we recorded it in consecutive steps. This is because the crystallization front propagates faster than the EELS data collection time (≈ 2 min). Therefore, we “froze” the reaction front by quenching the sample to 350 °C to collect STEM-EELS data. The lateral crystallization of a-Ge was resumed each time the temperature was increased back to 450 °C.

Fig. 4 shows false-color EELS intensity maps of Ag and Ge in the region nearby NP P3 along with HAADF STEM images during the various stages of the MIC reaction. The full set of data for P3 and P4 NPs are available in the supplement materials (fig. S4 and fig. S5). Raw EELS spectrum from a single pixel (marked by A in Fig. 4a0) of SI data is shown in Fig. 4d, while Fig. 4e shows the same spectrum after the PCA denoise routine. It is clear that Ge has a prominent volume plasmon peak at ≈ 16.1 eV (Fig. 4d) and a weak M-shell ionization edge at ≈ 29 eV (Fig. 4d, e). The Ag has a series of broad and weak (compared to Ge) plasmon resonances in the low loss region [24]. We used energy losses in the range of 3–4 eV for Ag mapping to avoid overlapping with the Ge plasmon signal. In this energy range, the loss structure of Ag has two plasmon excitations, namely the bulk plasmon at ≈ 3.8 eV [25] and the surface plasmon resonance peak (SPR) at ≈ 3.6 eV (Fig. 4e).

The dominant surface plasmon loss signal is clearly visible around the entire Ag NP P3 along with a weak Ag volume plasmon at stage 0 (Fig. 4b0). No distinguishable energy loss signal was registered from small Ag NPs, probably due to a low signal-to-noise ratio of the dataset. The Ge volume plasmon signal is firmly detected from the uncovered a-Ge substrate (Fig. 4c0). Furthermore, an outline of the small Ag NPs is visible in this map due to damping of the Ge plasmon signal in these regions. The first increase in temperature to 450 °C activated the a-Ge lateral crystallization, leading to the very first nuclei at the edge of the Ag NP (marked by solid arrows in Fig. 4b1). They are Ag-based as confirmed by the Ag plasmon map (Fig. 4b1). At the same time, part of

the Ag particle turns into pure Ge, as shown by the strong Ge plasmon peak (marked by dotted arrow in Fig. 4c1), along with the complete absence of Ag signal in that region (dotted arrow in Fig. 4b1). This means that the substitution of Ag by Ge in NP P3 has started. We believe that the crystallographic orientation of Ag facets plays a decisive role in this process, i.e., the process is activated on a preferred facet, leaving the rest of the surface of Ag NP unaffected.

During the subsequent stage of the MIC process, the outflow of Ag and its substitution with Ge in NP P3 (Fig. 4a2-c2) continued, resulting in the formation of an Ag-based crystallization front around NP P3. Both the outflow and substitution processes should occur simultaneously according to the law of conservation of matter. It is worth noting that the SPR peak of the parent Ag NP is clearly visible, along with the crystallization front at stage 2 (Fig. 4b2). This indicates that the process occurred under the Ag NP, namely within the volume of the Ge film, while the top surface of the Ag NP remains intact. At the next stage of the reaction, the crystallization front propagated towards a-Ge regions of the film, thus consuming fine Ag NPs (Fig. 4a3-c3) and leaving crystallized Ge behind. We assessed the average growth speed of the crystallization area from the series of images to be several nanometers per second. It should be noted that once the a-Ge was crystallized around NP P3, the Ag NP stopped generating nuclei and remained inactive. As a result, only a portion of Ag in 90 nm-sized NP P3 was consumed by the crystallization front, as follows from Fig. 4a3-c3.

The situation was somewhat different for NP P4. It has a smaller size (62 nm) and the entire amount of Ag was consumed by the crystallization front already during the first increase in temperature to 450 °C (fig. S5 in the supplement materials). This behavior is not obvious from the HAADF-STEM images since the contrast in this mode depends on both atomic number and thickness. Yet, it is evident from the Ag and Ge plasmon maps – no Ag was detected in P4, it is pure Ge (fig. S5 b1 and c1 in the supplement materials). The crystallization front is clearly visible around NP P4. It is worth mentioning that the c-Ge film has ≈ 20 % higher intensity of volume plasmon signal compared to its a-Ge counterpart with the same thickness (fig. S6 in the supplement materials). At the same time, we did not notice an appreciable shift of the peak at the amorphous-crystalline phase transition. A maximum of the plasmon peak for both a-Ge and c-Ge was measured at ≈ 16.2 eV at 350 °C.

3.4. Electron beam effect.

Great care was taken to control and minimize beam-induced effects, namely radiation damage and heating. Standard strategies based on decreasing the acceleration voltage, beam current and irradiation time, as well as a frequent comparison of morphologies in the area observed and in an unexposed region were used. No visible effect of the electron

Fig. 4. HAADF STEM images (a0-a3), false-color EELS intensity maps of Ag (b0-b3), and Ge (c0-c3) of NP P3 (Fig. 1d) at 350 °C showing the various stages of the MIC reaction. Single pixel EELS spectra (e, d) taken from the location indicated by (A) in (a0); (d) is the raw spectrum, (e) is the PCA-treated one. Rectangular regions in HAADF images (a0-a3) indicate the areas used for SI data acquisition. Solid arrows in (b1) mark AgGe nuclei, while the dotted arrows in (b1 and c1) denote the crystalline Ge part of NP P3.

beam on the MIC reaction was registered for a beam current density of $\approx 4 \times 10^4 \text{ A/m}^2$ routinely used for phase contrast TEM imaging and a probe current of 8 pA used in STEM-EELS spectral imaging. The reaction in the illuminated and unexposed regions was activated at the same temperature of $\approx 450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in both STEM and TEM *in situ* heating experiments, resulting in similar morphology over the whole Ag/Ge film (see Fig. S7 in the supplement materials). On the other hand, upon increasing the current density to $\approx 10^6 \text{ A/m}^2$ in TEM mode by focusing the beam to a nanoparticle triggered the MIC reaction at lower temperatures. Hence, a quantification of the beam-induced heating effect for Ag/Ge specimens was required.

Recently we measured the electron-beam-induced temperature increment of single AuGe nanoparticles in TEM and STEM modes [27]. No measurable change in the temperature of the NPs was registered in the STEM mode at conventional parameters of the electron beam and the raster scans. In TEM mode, the temperature of the NPs rose linearly with the e-beam current density. Calculations of the beam heating effect within theoretical approaches showed that the model of L. Liu and S. H. Risbud [28] could be used for assessing the upper limit of the beam-induced heating for nanoparticles in TEM. Hence, we applied this approach to Ag/Ge films that were used in the current work. The balance between the energy absorption and dissipation under electron beam irradiation results in the temperature increment ΔT in the following form [28].

$$\Delta T = \frac{3JQ}{8eK} R^2 \ln \left(1 + \frac{4Kt}{cdR^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where J is the current density, R is the radius of the illuminated area, e is the electron charge, d is the mass density, c is the specific heat, t is the time, K is the thermal conductivity, and Q is the total energy loss of the electron in the specimen. Details for calculating the energy loss Q could be found in Ref. [28].

Assuming that the energy is lost and dissipated in the Ge film, one can assess the ΔT value for different beam current densities and illuminated areas. The main uncertainty arises with the value of thermal conductivity of 10-nm-thick Ge film, which is not known precisely. According to literature, it varies from 56.4 W/mK [30] for crystalline Ge to 0.62–12 W/mK [31] for a-Ge films. With a thermal conductivity as low as $K = 0.62 \text{ W/mK}$, the local temperature increment of Ge film irradiated at $J = 4 \times 10^4 \text{ A/m}^2$ did not exceed $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is acceptable. We used $t = 100 \text{ s}$ and $R = 90 \text{ nm}$ in calculations to fit experimental parameters of high-resolution TEM imaging that were used in the work. It should be noted that the local temperature could rise by almost $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with the same beam focused to a spot with $R = 20 \text{ nm}$ ($J = 8 \times 10^5 \text{ A/m}^2$), which shows the importance of the careful control of illumination parameters in course of *in situ* TEM studies.

The displacement threshold of crystalline Ge for electron irradiation is $\approx 380 \text{ keV}$ [32] (assuming a threshold energy for the atomic displacement of 20 eV [28]), which is well above the primary beam energy of 200 keV used in the TEM study. At the same time, the sputtering threshold of Ge ($\approx 120 \text{ keV}$ [26,29]) is below the electron beam energy, and the sputtering of Ge should be taken into account. According to Ref. [26], the sputtering rate S is given approximately by:

$$S = \frac{J}{e} \frac{Z^2}{AE_0} \left(\frac{1}{E_s} - \frac{1}{E_{max}} \right) 3.54 \times 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2 \quad (2)$$

where Z is the atomic number, A is the atomic weight, E_0 is the incident energy, E_s is the sublimation energy per atom, and E_{max} is the maximum amount of transferred energy. The calculated value of the sputtering rate $S \approx 0.1 \text{ nm/min}$, thus allowing minutes of high-resolution TEM observation at 200 kV. In fact, this is the maximum value of the sputtering rate, and the 10 nm thick Ge film was pretty stable and did not collapse under the entire study.

The abovementioned considerations show that the electron beam did not fundamentally alter the crystallization behavior of a-Ge film under

an appropriate selection of the illumination parameters.

3.5. Post-heating characterization

Post-heating (S)TEM imaging, electron diffraction, and EDX chemical mapping have been applied for extending and verification the *in-situ* heating observations. First of all, the distribution of chemical elements in the regions of NPs P3 and P4 were measured by EDX mapping (Fig. 5). One can see that the distribution of Ag and Ge in the NPs is similar to that observed by low-loss EELS SI (Fig. 4 and Fig. S5 in supplement materials). Furthermore, EDX provides quantitative information on the composition in each point of the map, which is almost impossible to obtain by low-loss EELS SI. Thus, the concentration of Ge in the NP P3 varied from almost pure Ge in point B (99 at. %) to $\approx 32 \text{ at. } \%$ Ge in point C and $\approx 13 \text{ at. } \%$ Ge in point A (Fig. 5a). The NP P4 is almost pure Ge according to EDX measurements, the composition in region A (Fig. 5b) is 99.5 at. % of Ge. The same composition is observed in the crystallized areas of Ge film in the vicinity of NPs P3 and P4. At the same time, the composition at the reaction front (region B in Fig. 5b) was 24 at. % Ge, which coincides well with the eutectic composition of the bulk alloy (24.5 at. % Ge [33]). Therefore, all conditions for the formation of the liquid AgGe eutectic alloy were fulfilled at the reaction front, which additionally testifies the eutectic melting among the mechanisms of the reaction.

Secondly, we characterized the crystalline structure of the NP P4 and the surrounding area of the c-Ge film (Fig. 6a). Selected area electron diffraction studies showed that P4 is a single-crystalline diamond Ge phase, oriented along the [101] zone axis (Fig. 6c). The kinematically forbidden (020) reflections are visible in the diffraction pattern, yet upon tilting the specimen a few degrees around the [010] axis, the (020) reflections disappear. Therefore, we concluded that these reflections are due to double diffraction. Regarding the Ge crystallized in the vicinity of the NP, we noticed that it has the same orientation as the parent NP P4, and it is characterized by a heavily twinned microstructure of the film. Repeated single-orientation twins with twin planes ($1\bar{1}\bar{1}$) and ($11\bar{1}$) are clearly visible in the phase contrast image of the c-Ge film and shown by the FFT (Fig. 6b, d). As coherent twin boundaries are known to have a very small excess energy, the fact that they are being oriented perpendicular to the reaction front will facilitate its rapid propagation and growth of the crystalline Ge phase [34].

3.6. Discussion

As shown above, the MIC process proceeds in two distinct regimes for our configuration of the Ag/Ge film. In the first regime, the process occurs only at the metal–semiconductor interface, i.e. in the direction normal to the Ag/Ge film surface. This regime is activated at $\approx 200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which correlates well with the data reported in the literature [12,16,19]. The second regime involves the lateral crystallization of the a-Ge film. It occurs via formation and propagation of a crystallization front at temperatures above $\approx 400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and results in the complete crystallization of the a-Ge film. This second regime is self-sustained, i.e. the latent heat released at the crystallization front fuels the process. However, the advancement speed of the crystallization front is orders of magnitude lower than that of the explosive crystallization of pure a-Ge films. In the latter case, speeds of several meters per second have been reported [35], while our observation showed values on the order of nanometers per second. We believe that this is because Ag needs to be transferred through the Ge film volume in case of the MIC process. The difference in contact angles of the Ag-base phase with a-Ge and c-Ge drives the advancement of the crystallization front and defines its velocity, as was shown in Ref. [36] for the sister Au/Ge film.

The main finding of this study is revealing that the intermediate phase plays a role during the MIC reaction, which points out that the MIC process is a first-order, non-equilibrium solid–liquid–solid phase

Fig. 5. HAADF-STEM images (a, b) and false-color EDX chemical element maps (c, d) of the regions of NPs P3 and P4 at room temperature. Scale bar in (a) and (b) is 20 nm.

Fig. 6. (a) Bright-field TEM image of NP P4 oriented along the $[1\ 0\ 1]$ zone axis (b) Phase contrast TEM image of c-Ge in area II of (a), (c) selected area diffraction pattern from the Ag nanoparticle (area I in (a)), (d) Fourier transform of the crystallized Ge film located in the region labelled by the yellow square in (b). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

transformation, at least during the lateral crystallization of the a-Ge film. This is confirmed in several ways.

First, we unambiguously identified nuclei of AgGe hcp phase at the reaction front. The AgGe hcp phase is metastable, and it is typically found in high-pressure (5–7 GPa) experiments [37] or in rapidly quenched liquid eutectic alloys [38], but not at elevated temperatures. We are convinced that the sole path for obtaining the AgGe hcp phase in our conditions is the rapid crystallization of undercooled liquid AgGe eutectic alloy, which was formed at the expense of the excess energy of a-Ge. It is worth noting that the AgGe hcp phase was detected at the

dendrite growth front in nanosized Ag-Ge layered films at temperatures as low as 250 °C [12]. It was also concluded that its formation is the result of crystallization of a metastable liquid at the growth front. These observations complement and enhance the findings of the current study. Indeed, thin continuous layers of Ag and Ge, which were used in work [12], modeled the metal–semiconductor interface. As a result, the activation temperature of the MIC reaction in this configuration almost coincides with that observed in our specimens in the first regime. Furthermore, a decrease of the eutectic temperature by a few hundred degrees was reported for thin Ag/Ge films. Thus, continuous Ag/Ge

films with the thickness of Ge layer of 10 nm melted at a temperature of ≈ 480 °C [12], which supports the liquid phase mechanism of the MIC reaction. At the same time, we did not observe the equilibrium liquid alloy at the MIC reaction front at similar temperatures. We suppose that the configuration and thickness of Ag-Ge layers affect the melting process as was shown in Ref. [12], requiring additional studies to obtain further insight.

Second, both *in-situ* and *ex-situ* studies revealed that the a-Ge crystallization front is composed of Ag and Ge with the eutectic proportion of components. This makes possible the formation of a liquid phase at temperatures much lower than the melting points of Ag and Ge.

Finally, the morphology of the crystallized Ge film observed behind the crystallization front is the signature of rapidly solidified eutectic alloys, thus providing insight into the mechanism of the advancement of the reaction front.

At this point, there is one more issue that supports the liquid-phase mechanism of the MIC effect, which needs to be discussed, namely why fine Ag NPs (4–7 nm in size) remain inert at any temperature studied, while large Ag NPs (dozens-of-nanometer-sized) triggered the MIC reaction (figs. S3 and S7 in the supplement materials). On one hand, it is known that the solubility is greatly enhanced for nanomaterials [40]. For example, the amount of Ge dissolved in ≈ 10 nm Ag grains reaches 15–20 at.% already at 200–250 °C [12], which is close to the eutectic composition. If one considers eutectic melting as the formation and subsequent melting of solid solutions, then the small NPs should melt and trigger the crystallization of a-Ge film at temperatures as low as 200–250 °C. However, this has not occurred at any temperature used in the study. On the other hand, eutectic melting is a first-order phase transformation and requires formation of a two-component nucleus of a critical size. Therefore, the size of Ag nanoparticle must be larger than the size of the liquid phase nucleus, which is not our case. Indeed, the size of the eutectic alloy nuclei in the Ag/Ge films was ≈ 8 nm (Fig. 2b), while the size of fine Ag NPs was smaller than that value. As a result, fine Ag NPs were not able to form a liquid nucleus at any temperature studied and crystallize a-Ge film. It should be noted that we have previously observed a similar behavior for Au/Ge, Ag/Ge and Sn/Bi films, where the films with a metal thickness below a threshold (or critical) value did not melt at the eutectic temperature of the bulk alloy [41–43].

This analysis points out to the non-equilibrium melting of the AgGe eutectic alloy in the reaction zone as the most probable mechanism of the metal-induced crystallization in Ag/Ge films.

Surely, the factors driving the regimes in the MIC process require further studies. Nevertheless, we are confident that while the onset temperature of the reaction is specific for each binary couple, the complete crystallization of the a-Ge occurs at temperatures, which are specific to the configuration of the metal–semiconductor system and the thickness of a-Ge film. This is due to different nucleation and growth conditions at the metal–semiconductor interface and in the volume of the a-Ge film. If so, the classical theory of nucleation should be applied [39]. According to this theory, the formation of a critical nucleus of radius r requires additional energy to overcome the energy barrier ΔG , given by.

$$\Delta G = \frac{1}{3} 4\pi r^2 \sigma f(\theta) \quad (3)$$

where σ is the interfacial energy, $f(\theta)$ accounts for the shape of the nuclei, θ is the contact angle. This nucleation barrier is associated with the energy required for the creation of surface of a new phase, and it is smaller for heterogeneous nucleation (compared to homogeneous one) due to a smaller surface area of the nucleus to be created.

We suggest that for our configuration of Ag/Ge film, the first (low-temperature) regime of the reaction, which occurs at the metal–semiconductor interface, corresponds to a heterogeneous nucleation case, while the second regime, which is the lateral propagation of nuclei through thin Ge film, resembles a homogeneous nucleation event.

Indeed, a careful inspection of the morphology of the crystallization front (e.g. Fig. 4a2, a3 and fig. S5a1) shows that it composed of Ag-based grains with sizes equal to the granule size of as-deposited a-Ge film (Fig. 1e) and the size of the nuclei in Fig. 2b. Therefore, we may state that the nucleation of a new phase occurs in the whole volume of the granule, i.e. quasi homogeneously. The jump-like, granule-by-granule propagation of the crystallization front observed by *in situ* TEM supports this statement.

Another factor influencing the magnitude of the energy barrier in eq. (3) is the interfacial energy σ , which differs for the first and second regimes of the reaction, in our case. Thus, a new phase nucleating in the bulk of the film needs the energy to create the interface with either Ag or Ge. On the other hand, two-phase nuclei, which propagate through a-Ge films, have a substantial fraction of the surface in contact with vacuum, i.e. a free surface. As the free surface has typically greater excess energy when compared with the metal–semiconductor boundary, the mean interfacial energy σ is smaller for the first regime of the reaction. Each of these factors, namely the surface area and the interfacial energy, leads to a higher temperature required to ensure the propagation of nuclei in the lateral direction of the a-Ge film, as it was observed experimentally. Surely, the thickness of the a-Ge film and its morphology will influence the aforementioned energies. This interpretation provides a better understanding of the large scatter in MIC temperatures for the same couples registered via various experimental techniques [8–21].

4. Conclusions

In summary, we investigated the initial stages of the Ag-induced crystallization of amorphous Ge films by advanced TEM/STEM down to the atomic level. Our observations revealed the presence of two regimes in the MIC process for our configuration of the Ag/Ge film, namely a low-temperature regime (200–350 °C) occurring only at the metal–semiconductor interface and a second regime, which is related with the lateral crystallization of the a-Ge film activated at temperatures above ≈ 400 °C. Ag NPs triggered the MIC reaction and a distinct crystallization front with a eutectic ratio of Ag and Ge was observed around each of the NPs. A comprehensive study of the nucleation and growth of the crystalline Ge phase revealed that the process is intermediated by at least one metastable phase, which is hcp AgGe phase. The analysis of the data indicates that the hcp AgGe phase likely results from crystallization of non-equilibrium liquid eutectic alloy, which is formed at the expense of excess energy of a-Ge film, supporting, therefore, the liquid-phase mechanism of the MIC reaction. It was shown that the size of Ag NPs must exceed a critical value, which is ≈ 8 nm in our system, to activate the Ag-induced crystallization of a-Ge film.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aleksandr Kryshnal: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Sergiy Bogatyrenko:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Paulo Ferreira:** Validation, Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary material.pdf. File contains microscopic images, EELS spectra and chemical element maps to support and extend the main results discussed in the text. Video1.avi. Sequence of HR TEM images of Ag/Ge film at 450°C showing advancement of AgGe nuclei through a-Ge film. Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2022.154873>.

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